

**Two Major Challenges in Assessment Processes at
Secondary Level in Bangladesh:
Rote-memorization and High-stakes Examinations**

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INTRODUCTION

The secondary education system in Bangladesh is predominantly shaped by rote memorization and high-stakes examinations, which limit students' ability to think critically and contribute to intense academic pressure. These issues are exacerbated by an assessment model that prioritizes students' ability to recall information over understanding and application, thereby diminishing opportunities for creativity, independent thought, and problem-solving skills. Moreover, reliance on high-stakes exams as the primary measure of academic success places immense stress on students, often at the cost of their mental health and overall development. Addressing these challenges calls for a fundamental shift in the assessment paradigm. This paper proposes the adoption of an integrated assessment framework aimed at fostering critical thinking, reducing the emphasis on high-stakes testing, and ultimately creating a more balanced educational environment that supports holistic student development.

PROBLEM 1: ROTE MEMORIZATION AND LACK OF CRITICAL THINKING

DESCRIPTION OF THE ISSUE

The overwhelming reliance on rote memorization and the lack of emphasis on critical thinking abilities are relevant significant issues with Bangladesh's evaluation processes at the secondary level. The evaluation process largely gauges pupils' retention and replication of information verbatim. Students' independent thought, creativity, and problem-solving abilities are discouraged by this method.

PROBLEMATIC NATURE

A major issue is that this situation does not adequately prepare pupils for the rigors of the real world. Learning by rote encourages students to memorize information without fully grasping the meaning behind it. They have trouble transferring their knowledge to new contexts and developing their critical thinking skills as a result (Iqbal & Ahmad, 2015).

WHAT IS HAPPENING AND WHO IS AFFECTED

Students are frequently instructed to memorize a lot of material in order to pass tests in classrooms across Bangladesh. Teachers are under pressure to assure high pass rates, so they concentrate on teaching material that will be evaluated, leaving little time to encourage critical thinking. The demands of the modern labor market and higher education are not adequately prepared for by pupils as a result. Students, educators, and the institution as a whole are impacted by this problem.

PRESCRIBED SOLUTION: INTEGRATED ASSESSMENT FRAMEWORK

The adoption of an integrated assessment system is essential to resolving this problem. A range of assessment techniques that encourage critical thinking and problem-solving abilities would be incorporated into this framework. It would place a strong emphasis on evaluating students' conceptual understanding, information analysis skills, and ability to apply knowledge in practical settings. The integrated assessment framework would include components such as **project-based assessments, group discussions, presentations, case studies, and open-ended questions**. These methods would encourage students to think critically, evaluate information, collaborate, and express their ideas effectively (Angelo, 1995).

Figure 1: Factors of Implementing the Solution in Bangladeshi Education System

CONSTRAINTS AND POSSIBILITIES OF IMPLEMENTATION IN BANGLADESH

Constraints	Possibilities
<p>Traditional Mindset: Changes in mentality are necessary among all stakeholders, including teachers, students, parents, and policymakers, in order to implement the move from rote memorization to a critical thinking-based evaluation. It could be difficult to get over people's aversion to change (Mohiuddin, 2015).</p>	<p>Awareness and Advocacy: Support for the introduction of a more comprehensive evaluation system can be gained through raising awareness of the value of critical thinking skills in education among parents, students, and the general public (Poddar & Mizan, 2020).</p>
<p>Training and Professional Development: In order for teachers to successfully execute the integrated assessment framework, it is possible that they may need training and professional development. In order to ensure that classroom instructors have access to the resources they need, we must invest in teacher education programs and provide them with ongoing assistance (Mohiuddin, 2015).</p>	<p>Teacher Empowerment: Teachers' ability to successfully execute the integrated assessment framework will be improved by encouraging them to take part in professional development programs that concentrate on novel assessment techniques.</p>
	<p>Government Support: By setting policy guidelines and contributing funds for infrastructure development and training initiatives, the government may play a crucial role in fostering the changes that are required (Poddar & Mizan, 2020).</p>

PROBLEM 2: HIGH-STAKES EXAMINATIONS AND PRESSURE ON STUDENTS

DESCRIPTION OF THE ISSUE

The predominance of high-stakes exams and the pressure they place on students is another significant issue with Bangladesh's secondary assessment systems. The Secondary School Certificate (SSC) or Higher Secondary Certificate (HSC) tests, which are given at the conclusion of each academic year, are the primary exams used in the education system. These tests indicate a student's academic standing, likelihood of admission to a university, and future prospects.

PROBLEMATIC NATURE

The problem of high-stakes tests and the pressure they place on children is problematic for a number of reasons. First off, it fosters a climate of intense competition where test scores take precedence over all-around growth. This emphasis on one test performance hinders kids' overall development since it fails to accurately gauge their range of abilities, competencies, and interests. Second, students experience stress, worry, and mental health problems as a result of the great pressure to succeed on these important tests (Heissel et al., 2019).

WHAT IS HAPPENING AND WHO IS AFFECTED

Students in Bangladesh frequently experience extreme pressure to perform well on these important tests from their families, institutions, and the general public. The education system puts a lot of pressure on students to perform well on these exams, which causes students to narrowly focus on exam preparation at the detriment of other crucial components of education like critical thinking, creativity, and practical skills. This problem has an impact on children, parents, educators, and the entire educational system.

PRESCRIBED SOLUTION: CONTINUOUS AND COMPREHENSIVE ASSESSMENT

Implementing a constant and thorough evaluation method is crucial to addressing the issue of high stakes exams and the strain on pupils. Instead of depending exclusively on a single final exam, this strategy would incorporate continuing examinations throughout the school year (Singh & Pany, 2016). The continuous and comprehensive assessment approach would include **formative assessments**, such as **class quizzes, assignments, projects, and regular classroom assessments**. It would also incorporate **summative assessments**, but with reduced weightage compared to the current high-stakes exams (Chopra & Bhatia, 2021). Additionally, **performance-based assessments, portfolios, and self-assessments** could be included to provide a more holistic evaluation of students' progress. The pressure and anxiety that come with a single, demanding test would be lessened if evaluations were spaced out over the course of the academic year. It would provide a more thorough assessment of students' knowledge, abilities, and development across many academic areas.

Figure 2: Factors of Implementing the Solution in Bangladeshi Education System

CONSTRAINTS AND POSSIBILITIES OF IMPLEMENTATION IN BANGLADESH

Constraints	Possibilities
<p>Mindset Shift: Stakeholders, including lawmakers, school administrators, teachers, and parents, must undergo a considerable attitude shift in order to transition from a high-stakes testing system to a continuous and comprehensive assessment method. It may be difficult to persuade them of the advantages and get beyond their aversion to change (Rahman, 2018).</p>	<p>Policy Reforms: By implementing legislative measures that encourage and support the execution of frequent and thorough assessments, the government can play a key role. This can entail making changes to the policies governing exams, giving teachers instructions and training, and granting funds for infrastructure improvement (Mohiuddin, 2015)t.</p>
<p>Infrastructure and Resources: It would be necessary to have a sufficient infrastructure, including classrooms, technology, and resources, to do continuous and comprehensive assessments. It may be difficult to provide equal access to resources for all schools, even those in rural locations (Poddar & Mizan, 2020).</p>	<p>Teacher Training and Capacity Building: For the new assessment strategy to be successfully implemented, teachers would need support and training. Programs for ongoing professional development can give instructors the knowledge and abilities they need to create and use a variety of evaluations.</p> <p>Parent and Community Engagement: Raising awareness among parents and communities about the benefits of continuous and comprehensive assessments can garner support and generate a collective understanding of the need for a more holistic approach to evaluation (Mohiuddin, 2015).</p>

CONCLUSION

Students' overall development and future readiness are hampered by the excessive emphasis on rote memorization and the disregard for critical thinking assessment in secondary education in Bangladesh. To overcome these difficulties, an integrated evaluation system that encourages critical thinking and problem-solving abilities can be introduced. Although there are limitations, government assistance, teacher empowerment, and awareness-building initiatives can help to clear the way for successful implementation and, in the end, give students a more thorough and relevant educational assessment experience. High stakes exams are common, and the pressure they place on secondary school children in Bangladesh hinders their overall development and exacerbates mental health problems. These difficulties can be overcome by implementing a continual and thorough assessment method. Although there are limitations, legislative changes, teacher development, and parent/community involvement can help to establish an environment that is favorable for the effective adoption of this novel evaluation system. We can create a more balanced and supportive educational environment that emphasizes holistic development and equips students for future success by giving priority to a thorough evaluation of students' progress and lowering the reliance on high-stakes exams.

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